

ARAMID FIBERS CHARACTERISTICS AND THEIR INFLUENCES ON
COMPOSITES PART 1 THE STUDY OF ARAMID FIBERS' SKIN-
CORE STRUCTURE AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The skin-core structure of aramid fibers was mainly researched by means of Scanning Auger Microprober (SAM). Transmitted Polarized Light Microscope and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). It is observed that the skin of aramid fibers is more complete fibrillar, and the packing of macromoleculars in fiber core is looser than in the skin. Owing to this special structure, aramid fibers possess longitudinal strength, the rather weak transverse strength, the $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds on fiber surface when stressed, and the fiber skin is easily separated from its core.

INTRODUCTION

Because of low density, high specific stiffness, low thermal expansion coefficient, low creep and excellent dielectric property, aramid fibers are reputed as high technologic fibers or the third generation fibers. Aramid fiber epoxy composites are used proadly in aricraft and aerospace applications.

During the past twenty years, a great deal valuable research work has been done on the aramid fibers' structures^{1,2}, the modifying mechanical properties of aramid fiber composites³⁻⁶, and their environment aging behavior⁷⁻⁹. But there were limited reports about theinfluences of characteristics of aramid fibers structure on the mechanical properties and processability of aramid epoxy composites.

Fiber reinforcement is one of the most important part in composites. Besides understanding the influences of its properties, contents, orientation on properties of composites, further studing the structure-properties of aramid fibers and their influences on composites will be helpful to control and improve the quality of aramid epoxy composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three kinds of aramid fibers were chosen for this investigation:
Kevlar 49 (1420-1000-0-965, Du Pont Co.)
Twaron HM (Enka Co.)
Fanglun 1 (Shanghai Research Institute of Synthetic Fibers)
The distribution of C element in fiber cross-section was analyzed by PHI 595 Multiprober (Perkin-Elementer Co.)

The method for observing the special deformation of aramid fibers involves encapsulating a single Kevlar 49 fiber in an epoxy coupon, and curing at a definite condition. The fibers deformation resulted from curing shrinkage can be observed with both transmitted and polarized transmitted light through a microscope (XPA-1 Transmitted Reflected Light Microscope, SuZhou No. 267 National Factory). For SEM studies (Stereoscan 250 Mhz Scanning Electron Microscope, Cambridge Co.), the fracture surfaces were coated with gold.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The distribution of C element in aramid fibers cross-section
Before SAM occurred, it was rather difficult to study the element distribution in a 10-30A deep, and 0.1 μ m wide area.

The C element distribution in the cross-section of three kinds of fibers is shown in Fig.1a-c. It is clear that: (1) The C element distribution in fibers is not even. The peaks at two sides of the curves indicate that the number of C atoms detected by Auger electrons in the fiber skin is more than that in the core. These results confirm the Morgan's model¹, well that aramid fibers consist of a more complete fibrillar skin and a looser crystalline core. (2). There are different characteristics in the skin-core structure of the three kinds of fibers. The skin of Kevlar 49 and Fanglun 1 is thicker than that of Twaron HM; and in the core the C element distribution of Fanglun 1 and Twaron HM is more uneven than that of Kevlar 49. It indicates that the macromolecular packing in the core of Kevlar 49 is evenner than the others. (3) The skin-core structure of Kevlar 49 is more typical than the others. The skin-core structure of aramid fibers is different from that of carbon fibers. The skin-core structure of carbon fibers is resulted from their preoxygenation, carbonation, and graphitization. For high tensile strength carbon fibers with good carbonation, the C element distribution in the fiber cross-section tends to even. But the skin-core structure of aramid fibers is caused by their rigid macromolecular and spinning process.

2. The unique deformation and failure mode of aramid fibers

(1) $\pm 45^\circ$ helical surface folds

Sustained by an additional surface stress, aramid fiber surface occurs an unique helical folds which form at both (+) and (-) 45° to fiber axis (Fig. 2a). Under polarized light, however, fiber microcracks are easily detected due to their birefringence with $\pm 45^\circ$ bright lines (Fig. 2b). This phenomenon confirms that the skin-core structure of aramid fibers is very sensitive to additional stress at the fiber surface. The deformations under bending stress and shear stress imposed by knots in a single filament are observed as Fig. 3a-3d. The unique $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds occurring in the sharply curved region are the regular separation of fiber skin from its core. Owing to the brittleness of carbon fibers, a knot in single filament are observed as Fig. 3a-3d. The unique $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds occurring in the sharply curved region are the regular separation of fiber skin from its core. Owing to the brittleness of carbon fibers; a knot in single filament can not be got. The knot can be got in a single glass filament, but no unique $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds can be observed. These results also indicate that the skin-core structure of aramid fibers is rather easy to be revealed by the separation of skin from its core, and finally the whole fiber failure.

In addition, the differences of the structure among three aramid fibers can be characterized with their different characteristics of skin-core separation. The deformation behavior of Twaron HM is basically similar to Kevlar 49, but the fiber axial cracks at the compressed side occur while $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds appear (Fig. 3c). It demonstrates that the combination of fibrills in the skin of Twaron HM is not as strong as that

in Kevlar 49. As for Fanglun 1 (Fig.3d), the number of the $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds on its surface is lesser than the others, and appears nearly brittle break in tension side. This phenomenon indicates that the skin-core structure of Fanglun 1 is not so obvious, therefore the axial tensile strength of fiber skin is low, and fiber toughness is not so good.

(2) The peeling of the fiber skin

From Fig.4-5, the fibrillar ($\sim 0.1\mu\text{m}$) in the skin teared from the aramid fiber surface can be seen. This unique deformation mode, which never occurs in carbon fibers and glass fibers, results in high longitudinal tensile strength, low transverse strength, and high anisotropic. It can also be demonstrated from topography of fibers cut crosswise (Fig.6a-d). The crosswise of T-300 carbon fiber show brittleness, but the topography of aramid fibers exhibits toughness with fibrillation and axial peeling of fiber skin. Meanwhile, the characteristics of Twaron HM is similar to Kevlar 49 in cut crosswise topography, but Fanglun 1 exhibits more serious fibrillation.

(3) axial splitting

Breaking under longitudinal tensile stress, aramid fibers exhibit a unique extensive splitting in this direction (Fig.7a). This phenomenon further demonstrates that the difference of the skin-core structure between aramid fibers and carbon fibers.

CONCLUSION

Scanning Auger Microprobe, Polarized Transmitted Light Microscope and Scanning Electron Microscope are effective tools which can be used to satisfactorily characterize the skin-core structure of aramid fibers. These studies indicate that the skin of aramid fibers is more complete fibrillar and the core is crystalline. The macromolecular packing in the core is looser than in the skin. This special skin-core structure of aramid fibers results in the unique mechanical characteristics which includes high longitudinal strength, low transverse strength, easily separation of skin from its core, and axial splitting. These characteristics must affect the mechanical properties and processability of aramid epoxy composites.

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1a. Kevlar 49

1b. Twaron HM

1c. FangLun 1

Fig.1. The C element distribution in cross-section of aramid fibers

2a. Transmitted light micrograph (400x)

2b. Polarized light micrograph (400x)

Fig.2. $\pm 45^\circ$ helical folds on Kevlar 49 fiber surface caused by epoxy curing shrinkage

3a. Kevlar 49

3b. S-Glass

3c. Twaron HM

3d. FangLun 1

Fig.3. The topography of knots in single filament of aramid fibers and glass fiber

Fig.4. The axial peeling of skin from Kevlar 49 fiber

Fig.5. The fibrillation in Kevlar 49 fiber skin

6a. Kevlar 49

6b. T-300

6c. Twaron HM

6d. FangLun 1

Fig.6. The topography of fiber's cut crosswise

7a. Kevlar 49

7b. T-300

Fig.7. SEM micrography of fractured ends of single filaments broken in tension